

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing as Complementary Medicine in the Rapid Recovery of Severe Lung Infection: A Case Report

Mohandas Baliga¹, Venkata Satyanarayana Nanduri²

¹Certified YPV Healer & Senior YPV Trainer, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

²Consultant, Research & Publications, YPV Ashram, Sri Ramana Trust, Thally-635118, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

Background: Lung infections are a major cause of morbidity worldwide, often requiring prolonged antibiotic therapy. Complementary therapies such as Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing have shown promise in accelerating recovery.

Case Presentation: A 40-year-old female presented with severe cough, breathlessness, and lung infection diagnosed as pollen allergy. Despite four months of antibiotics, her condition worsened, leaving her weak and fearful of survival.

Intervention: Certified YPV healer initiated healing protocols including YPV Psychotherapy YPV L3, YPV L2, Healer Development Level 1 (HDP L1), and stress energy removal. Twelve sessions were conducted over ten days, alongside daily YPV sadhana practices such as rhythmic breathing.

Results: Within three sessions, the patient reported dramatic improvement, discontinued medication, and regained normal appetite and energy. Seven years post-intervention, she remains symptom-free and has become a healer herself.

Conclusion: This case highlights the potential of YPV healing as a complementary therapy for lung infections, warranting further clinical research.

KEYWORDS: Lung infection, pollen allergy, Yoga Prana Vidya System ®, YPV ®, complementary therapy,

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
27 April 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Lung Infections

Lung infections, including pneumonia and bronchitis, are among the leading causes of global morbidity and mortality. They are triggered by bacterial, viral, or fungal pathogens and often require prolonged antibiotic therapy, which can lead to resistance and adverse side effects. Chronic respiratory infections impose a significant economic burden and reduce quality of life [1]. The increasing incidence of antibiotic-resistant strains complicates treatment, highlighting the urgent need for effective stewardship programs and research into novel antimicrobial agent [1, 2]. The World Health Organization reports that lower respiratory tract infections remain one of the top causes of death worldwide [3].

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV)

Yoga Prana Vidya is an integrative energy-based healing system rooted in yogic traditions [4]. It emphasizes regulation of prana (life force) through breathing, meditation, and

energy transmission [5,6]. Recent studies have documented YPV's role in managing chronic illnesses, including cancer, autoimmune disorders, and respiratory conditions, by harmonizing physiological and psychological states [7-9]. Case reports suggest YPV can accelerate recovery and reduce dependence on medication [10-15].

CASE PRESENTATION

Background information:

The patient, aged 40 years, female, housewife, developed severe cough and breathlessness in December 2017. Despite four months of antibiotics in conventional treatment, her condition worsened, with X-ray showing lung infection. She feared mortality due to lack of improvement. She approached a Certified YPV healer to conduct YPV energy healing sessions for improving her condition.

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing as Complementary Medicine in the Rapid Recovery of Severe Lung Infection: A Case Report

YPV Intervention

The Certified YPV Healer acted immediately upon patient's request, and started YPV healing intervention as per the following particulars.

- **Start date:** 23 March 2018
- **Protocols used:** YPV Psychotherapy, YPV L3, YPV L2, HDP L1, stress energy removal protocols.
- **Sessions:** 12 sessions over 10 days, each 30 minutes
- **Self-practice:** As advised by the YPV healer, the patient did Rhythmic Yogic Breathing 4–5 times daily

RESULTS

- Improvement noted within 3 sessions; breathlessness resolved, fatigue reduced, appetite normalized.
- Medication discontinued after 3 days.
- Complete recovery within 10 days.
- Follow up showed sustained wellness for 7 years; patient later became a YPV healer.

DISCUSSION

This case demonstrates YPV's potential as a complementary therapy for lung infections. Similar case reports have documented YPV's efficacy in acute conditions such as COVID, advanced cancer, brain stroke [8–10]. The mechanisms may involve improved autonomic regulation, stress reduction, and enhanced immune resilience. Further controlled studies are needed to validate these findings. Integrating YPV with conventional medicine could reduce antibiotic dependence and improve patient outcomes. Comparable integrative approaches in respiratory care have shown promise in reducing hospitalization and enhancing recovery[16].

CONCLUSION

YPV healing facilitated rapid recovery in a patient with severe lung infection unresponsive to antibiotics. This case underscores the importance of exploring complementary therapies such as YPV in respiratory medicine.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The patient is acknowledged for her contributions on condition of anonymity. Our thanks are also to Sri Raman Trust (Thally-635118) the copy right owners of the terms Yoga Prana Vidya System ® and YPV ®.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

None declared.

Funding

No funding received.

REFERENCES

- I. Peter B. Understanding Lung Infections: A Comprehensive Overview of Respiratory Diseases. *J Respir Med*, 2024;6(6):45–52.
- II. Niederman MS, Torres A. Respiratory infections. *Eur Respir Rev*. 2022;31(166):220150.
- III. WHO. Global burden of respiratory infections. WHO Report. 2023.
- IV. Devpriya S, Verma S. Prana Vidya in integrative health. *Int J Health Sci Res*. 2025;15(9):932.
- V. Neravetla J, Nanduri VS. A study into the successful treatment of some difficult Medical cases using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing System as alternative medicine. *Int J Sci Eng Res*, 2019, 10 (7):882-887
- VI. Nanduri VS, Vasavda A. Successful healing treatment of high blood cholesterol levels and asthma using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) system: A case study of self-healing. *Panacea Journal of Medical Sciences*,2019;9(3): 131-137
- VII. Neravetla J, Nanduri, VS. Role of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing Techniques in Emergency and First Aid: A Summary of Case Reports. *International Journal of Medical Science and Health Research*,2020; 4(3), 133-146
- VIII. Nanduri VS, Karnani V. Successful and speedy recovery of COVID patients using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing. *Covid-19*, 2020; 1(4):78-82 Doi: <http://doi.org/10.18231/j.covid.2020.005>
- IX. Jain V, Bindal S, Bhatia PK, Nanduri VS. Managing pain and side effects of a Hodgkin lymphoma female patient undergoing Chemotherapy using Yoga Prana Vidya System as complementary medicine: A case report. *International Journal of Medical Sciences and Academic Research*, 2(05):5-11
- X. Nayak L, Nanduri VS. A Case Study of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing Modalities Used Successfully In The Treatment of A Female Patient of Transient Ischemic Attack (TIA) With History of Sinus Tachycardia(ST). *Int J of Med Sci and Den Res*, 2022, 5(3):19-28. Available <http://www.ijmsdr.org/>
- XI. Dube N, Ramya A, Venkata Satyanarayana Nanduri. Successful application of Yoga Prana Vidya therapy and energy healing techniques in de-addiction: An analysis of case series. *Int J Intg Med Sci*, 2022;9(2):1016-1022. DOI: 10.16965/ijims.2022.101
- XII. Atheesh Kumar M, Saloni Dilip Shah, Nanduri, VS. A Case of Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease [Nafld]: Successful Treatment Using Yoga Prana Vidya Healing Without Surgical or Medical Intervention. *Clinical Medicine And Health*

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing as Complementary Medicine in the Rapid Recovery of Severe Lung Infection: A Case Report

- Research Journal, 2022; 2(5):183-186
<https://doi.org/10.18535/cmhrj.v2i5.81>
- XIII. Anur A, Nanduri VS. A case of ulcerative proctosigmoiditis healed successfully using yoga prana vidya healing system as alternate medicine. World Journal of Advanced Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 2022; 3(1):78-82
<https://zealjournals.com/wjapmr/sites/default/files/WJAPMR-2022-0038.pdf> DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.53346/wjapmr.2022.3.1.0038>
- XIV. Parikh S, Vasavda D, Nayak L, Jayachander Reddy N, Satyanarayana Nanduri V. Successful Healing Treatment of Renal Calculi (Kidney Stones) using Yoga Prana Vidya System Protocols: A Case Series Study. JNR [Internet]. 2023 May 23 [cited 2023 Jun. 22];23(2):637-45. Available from:
<https://www.informaticsjournals.com/index.php/jnr/article/view/32066>
- XV. Shah T, Nanduri VS. A case of chocolate ovarian cyst: successful healing using yoga prana vidya healing protocols as alternative medicine. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and life sciences, 2023; 09 (07):152-156
- XVI. Vel A, Nanduri VS,(2025). Complete Remission of Stage IV Lung Cancer, Asthma and Septic Shock in the right limb Using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing as complementary medicine: A Case Report, Journal of Carcinogenesis, Vol.24, No.9s, 597-606

Annexure 1: Patient Feedback dt 16 Dec 2025

“In December 2017, I suddenly developed a dry cough. Initially, I was put on cough syrups and medicines, which later escalated to antibiotics. This continued until March 2018, but the cough never stopped. Most of the time, I felt drowsy due to the heavy medication, and the moment the medicines were stopped, the cough would return. I became extremely weak and exhausted. An X-ray showed that my lungs were filled with infection. Based on my symptoms, doctors suggested it could be a pollen allergy. After four long months of continuous medication with no relief, I genuinely felt I might not survive.

Around this time, our ashramites returned and we had a get-together. After the programme, I shared my condition with ... YPV Healer Sir. He was upset that I hadn't informed him earlier and immediately started healing that very night — 23rd March 2018. What months of medication could not do, his healing did. Within just three days, I felt a remarkable improvement — no breathlessness, no fatigue, and my appetite returned to normal. He continued the healing for another ten days, and soon I was completely off medication. This experience was nothing short of a miracle for me. I remain deeply grateful for his healing and grace. — XXX

I no longer have the medical reports with me, but one thing I am absolutely certain of—your healing made a real and powerful difference in my recovery.

XXX 16 Dec 2025